

SYNTHESIS OF 6-HALOGENATED 2:3-DISUBSTITUTED QUINAZOL-4-ONES. PART III*

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Synthesis of 6-chloro- and 6-bromo-2-methyl-3-substituted phenylquinazol-4-ones is described.

The present investigation is an extension of our previous work on synthesis of differently benz-substituted quinazolone derivatives (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 199, 483). A contributory factor to the medicinal properties of some well-known drugs like atebriane, paludrine, chloromycetin is attributed to the presence of chlorine as a substituent in their respective molecules. Further, the products obtained by the chemical investigation of *Arboria correa*, a plant known for its medicinal efficacy in Ayurveda have been found to be 2:3-substituted quinazolone derivatives (Mrs. D. Chakravarti and co-workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3337). Hence, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise such quinazolone derivatives with chlorine as a substituent in the benzene ring of the quinazolone molecule. Analogous quinazolone derivatives with bromine as a substituent have also been synthesised.

Arrangements are being made to screen these compounds for their medicinal properties.

These 6-chloro- or 6-bromo-2:3-substituted quinazolones have been obtained by condensing N-aceto-5-chloro- or -5-bromo-anthranilic acid with different amines, following the method already described in our previous communication (*loc. cit.*). 5-Chloro-N-acetoanthranilic acid required for the purpose was obtained by chlorination of N-aceto-*o*-toluidide followed by oxidation of 2-acetamino-5-chlorotoluene, using neutral potassium permanganate (Tomisek and Christiansen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 2424). 5-Bromo-N-acetoanthranilic acid was similarly prepared (Bogert and Hand, *ibid.*, 1905; 27, 1480).

All the quinazolones described in this paper have been reported for the first time excepting 3-phenyl- and 3-*o*-tolyl-6-bromo-2-methylquinazol-4-ones (Bogert and Hand, *ibid.*, 1906, 28, 103).

EXPERIMENTAL

6-Chloro- and 6-bromo-quinazol-4-ones obtained are described in a tabular form to avoid repetition.

[X = Cl or Br ; R = substituted phenyl group].

* The first two papers on this subject are to be considered as Part I and Part II of this series.

TABLE I
6-Chloro-2-methyl-3-(R)-substituted-quinazol-4-ones and their hydrochlorides.

R =	M.P.	Crystalline form.	Formula.	Found.	Calcd.
1. -C ₆ H ₅	163°	Pale yellow small needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl	N, 9.8% Cl, 12.7	N, 10.4% Cl, 13.1
Hydrochloride of 1	241°	Colorless small needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl.HCl	Equiv. 307.0	Equiv. 307.0
2. -C ₆ H ₄ .OCH ₃ (p)	172°	Straw coloured granules	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	N, 8.9% Cl, 11.6	N, 9.3% Cl, 11.8
Hydrochloride of 2	237° (decomp.)	Light white granules	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.HCl	Equiv. 335.5	Equiv. 337.0
3. -C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃ (o)	167°	Light white granules	C ₁₈ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl	N, 9.4% Cl, 12.3	N, 9.8% Cl, 12.5
Hydrochloride of 3	238° (decomp.)	Small plates	C ₁₈ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl.HCl	Equiv. 317.3	Equiv. 321.0
4. -C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃ (m)	179°	Pale yellow soft needles	C ₁₈ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl	N, 9.3% Cl, 12.3	N, 9.8% Cl, 12.5
5. -C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃ (p)	164°	White shining plates	C ₁₈ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl	N, 9.2 Cl, 12.2	N, 9.8 Cl, 12.5
Hydrochloride of 5	235° (decomp.)	White granules	C ₁₈ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl.HCl	Equiv. 318.1	Equiv. 321.0
6. -C ₆ H ₄ .Cl (o)	158°	White lustrous granules	C ₁₈ H ₈ ON ₂ Cl ₂	N, 8.6% Cl, 22.7	N, 9.2% N, 23.3
Hydrochloride of 6	235° (decomp.)	Colorless shining granules	C ₁₈ H ₈ ON ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	Equiv. 336.2	Equiv. 341.5
7. -C ₆ H ₄ .Cl (m)	175°	Dull white needles	C ₁₈ H ₈ ON ₂ Cl ₂	N, 8.7% Cl, 22.8	N, 9.4% Cl, 23.3
Hydrochloride of 7	254° (decomp.)	Light white granules	C ₁₈ H ₈ ON ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	Equiv. 336.92	Equiv. 341.5
8. -C ₆ H ₄ .NO ₂ (p)	246°	Yellowish brown needles	C ₁₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	N, 13.1% Cl, 10.8	N, 13.3% Cl, 11.3
9. -C ₆ H ₄ .N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ (p)	210°	Bibish green needles	C ₁₉ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl	N, 11.8 Cl, 10.2	N, 12.3 Cl, 10.4
Hydrochloride of 9	234° (decomp.)	Small colorless needles	C ₁₉ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl.HCl	Equiv. 373.1	Equiv. 378.0

* Equiv. found by titrations.

TABLE II
6-Bromo-2-methyl-R-(substituted)-quinazol-4-ones and their hydrochlorides.

R =	M.P.	Crystalline form.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1. $-C_6H_5$ Hydrochloride of 1	186° 245° (decomp.)	Pale yellowish small needles small needles	$C_{13}H_{11}ON_2Br$ $C_{12}H_{10}ON_2ClBr$	Br, 25.3% Equiv. 347.7	Br, 25.4% Equiv. 351.5
2. $-C_6H_4.OCH_3$ (p)	181°	Colorless small needles	$C_{16}H_{13}O_2N_2Br$	N, 7.7% Br, 23.0 Equiv. 376.4	N, 8.1% Br, 23.2 Equiv. 381.5
Hydrochloride of 2	233° (decomp.)	Colorless granules	$C_{14}H_{11}O_2N_2ClBr$	Equiv. 376.4	Equiv. 381.5
3. $-C_6H_4.CH_3$ (o) Hydrochloride of 3	146° 241° (decomp.)	White small needles Colourless crystals	$C_{16}H_{13}ON_2Br$ $C_{15}H_{11}ON_2ClBr$	Br, 24.1% Equiv. 361.5	Br, 24.3% Equiv. 365.5
4. $-C_6H_4.CH_3$ (m)	165°	Pale yellowish soft needles	$C_{16}H_{13}ON_2Br$	N, 8.0% Br, 24.2 Equiv. 363.2	N, 8.5% Br, 24.3 Equiv. 365.5
Hydrochloride of 4	236° (decomp.)	Feathery plates	$C_{16}H_{11}ON_2ClBr$	Equiv. 363.2	Equiv. 365.5
5. $-C_6H_4.CH_3$ (p)	131°	Yellow needles	$C_{16}H_{13}ON_2Br$	N, 8.1% Br, 23.7	N, 8.5% Br, 24.3
Hydrochloride of 5	245° (decomp.)	Long soft needles	$C_{16}H_{11}ON_2ClBr$	Equiv. 360.4	Equiv. 365.5
6. $-C_6H_4.NO_2$ (p)	255°	Yellowish brown shining needles	$C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_3Br$	N, 11.5% Br, 21.7	N, 11.7% Br, 22.2
7. $-C_6H_4.Cl$ (o)	176°	Lustrous granules	$C_{15}H_{10}ON_2ClBr$	N, 7.5% Total halogen, 33.0 Equiv. 382.2	N, 8.0% Total halogen, 33.1 Equiv. 386
Hydrochloride of 7	237° (decomp.)	White granules	$C_{15}H_{11}ON_2Cl_2P$	Equiv. 382.2	Equiv. 386
8. $-C_6H_4.Cl$ (m)	196°	Yellowish needles	$C_{13}H_{10}ON_2ClBr$	N, 7.6% Total halogen, 33.7 Equiv. 388.2	N, 8.0% Total halogen, 33.1 Equiv. 386
Hydrochloride of 8	255° (decomp.)	Long colorless needles	$C_{15}H_{11}ON_2Cl_2Br$	Equiv. 388.2	Equiv. 386
9. $-C_6H_4.N(C_2H_5)_2$ (p)	227°	Yellowish green needles	$C_{18}H_{20}ON_2Br$	N, 10.3% Br, 20.2	N, 10.9% Br, 20.7
Hydrochloride of 9	247° (decomp.)	Colorless granules	$C_{19}H_{21}ON_2ClBr$	Equiv. 417.2	Equiv. 422.5

* Equiv. found by titrations.